

Multiple Organ Manifestation in Neonatal Lupus Erythematosus: Report of Two Cases

Authors : A. Lubis, R. Widayanti, Z. Hikmah, A. Endaryanto, A. Harsono, A. Harianto, R. Etika, D. K. Handayani, M. Sampurna

Abstract : Neonatal lupus erythematosus (NLE) is a rare disease marked by clinical characteristic and specific maternal autoantibody. Many cutaneous, cardiac, liver, and hematological manifestations could happen with affect of one organ or multiple. In this case, both babies were premature, low birth weight (LBW), small for gestational age (SGA) and born through caesarean section from a systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) mother. In the first case, we found a baby girl with dyspnea and grunting. Chest X ray showed respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) great I and echocardiography showed small atrial septal defect (ASD) and ventricular septal defect (VSD). She also developed anemia, thrombocytopenia, elevated C-reactive protein, hypoalbuminemia, increasing coagulation factors, hyperbilirubinemia, and positive blood culture of Klebsiella pneumonia. Anti-Ro/SSA and Anti-nRNP/sm were positive. Intravenous fluid, antibiotic, transfusion of blood, thrombocyte concentrate, and fresh frozen plasma were given. The second baby, male presented with necrotic tissue on the left ear and skin rashes, erythematous macula, atrophic scarring, hyperpigmentation on all of his body with various size and facial haemorrhage. He also suffered from thrombocytopenia, mild elevated transaminase enzyme, hyperbilirubinemia, anti-Ro/SSA was positive. Intravenous fluid, methyprednisolone, intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG), blood, and thrombocyte concentrate transfusion were given. Two cases of neonatal lupus erythematosus had been presented. Diagnosis based on clinical presentation and maternal auto antibody on neonate. Organ involvement in NLE can occur as single or multiple manifestations.

Keywords : neonatus lupus erythematosus, maternal autoantibody, clinical characteristic, multiple organ manifestation

Conference Title : ICAAIR 2014 : International Conference on Allergy, Asthma, Immunology and Rheumatology

Conference Location : Singapore, SG

Conference Dates : July 05-06, 2014